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This issue of Harmful Algae News marks its 20th anniversary. It also marks the introduction of a new layout and the introduction of a new on-line format. We hope you will like the new formats.

A newsletter for the HAB community was first broached in Takamatsu, Japan, in 1987 and fully formulated at an IOC-SCOR Workshop in Newport, Rhode Island (USA) in November 1991. The first HAN issues were published as a supplement to UNESCO's International Marine Science newsletter, which ceased to exist many years ago. Very few other newsletters have survived as long as HAN in IOC and UNESCO.

A unique aspect about HAN is the dedication of our Editor Tim Wyatt. Tim has from day one taken his job very seriously and has only received very symbolic benefits from the IOC. The IOC wish to express its deep appreciation of Tim Wyatt's unique effort.

Another remarkable aspect is that HAN has survived as a printed newsletter despite the informatics revolution. However, every year the pressure to go e-publishing increases due to the rising cost of postage and with this issue we will introduce the option of subscrib-

ing to HAN electronically only. This will save resources. For those that prefer a printed copy and for libraries it will still be possible to subscribe to the printed HAN. You will have a chance to try the new on-line format and if it suits you let us know to which e-mail address you wish to receive HAN in the future. On the back page of this issue you will find further information on how to modify your subscription.

HAN has around 2000 subscribers for the printed version and this has been very stable over the 20 years. At the biennial reviews of HAN by the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB), the Panel has taken this as an indication that the newsletter continues to fill an important role for the HAB research and man-

agement community. A role that is complementary to, and in between, those of the peer reviewed journals and the list servers such as phycotoxins, ALGAL-L, and ISSHA.

IOC is pleased that the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) uses HAN as its newsletter as it is both practical to the reader and meaningful from a resource point of view.

We hope HAN will continue to be useful to its readers and remind you that you are always welcome to send us ideas, proposals, and constructive criticism. Technology today offers new opportunities to stay connected across the globe and we welcome your thoughts on how we can make the most of them to share and benefit from one another's experiences.

On behalf of Editor Tim Wyatt, the teams at the IOC Science and Communication Centres in Vigo and Copenhagen, the IOC and UNESCO staff in Paris that handle mailing list and printing, and the leadership of IPHAB, thanks to you all for all your contributions over the past 20 years.

Henrik Enevoldsen, IOC of UNESCO

Toxicity and paralytic toxin profile in *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* and violet oyster in Bahía de Acapulco, Guerrero, Mexico

Harmful algae blooms are common events along the coasts of Guerrero. Since 1991, the local public health laboratory, "Dr. Galo Soberón y Parra", has monitored for red tide-forming species and PSP toxin-producing species along the southwestern coast of Mexico, including toxicity in several marine bivalves. The most common toxic dinoflagellates responsible for red tides in this area are the fish-toxic dinoflagellate *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* and the paralytic shellfish toxin-producers *Gymnodinium catenatum* and *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* [1,2]. Sometimes, these three species occur simultaneously along this coast [3].

The first bloom of *Gymnodinium catenatum* was observed in 1999 [4]; its incidence has been increasing since then [2]. *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* is broadly distributed along the Pacific coast of Mexico [1,2,3,5]. *Gymnodinium catenatum* and *P. bahamense* var. *compressum* are the main species causing paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) along the coasts of the States of Guerrero and Oaxaca.

Two varieties of *Pyrodinium* (*bahamense* and *compressum*) have been recognized [5]. The first extensive outbreak of the var. *compressum* occurred between Zihuatanejo, Guerrero and El Bejuco, Michoacán in November 1996; toxicity ranged from 520 to 6337 µg STXeq 100 g⁻¹ in bivalves, and there were six human fatalities and numerous sick people [6]. Eight blooms of var. *compressum* have since occurred

Fig. 1. Sampling stations: (1) Bahía de Acapulco, (2) La Prietilla, (3) La Palmita, (4) Punta Pilares, (5) La Rana, (6) Caja del Muerto, and (7) Punta Bruja.

in Bahía de Acapulco [1,3], with toxins in marine bivalves ranging from 21 to 7309 µg STXeq 100 g⁻¹; the highest toxicity occurred in the violet oyster in November 2001 at Las Palmitas, Acapulco.

As part of a continuing toxic microalgae monitoring program, a red tide of *P. bahamense* var. *compressum* was detected in July 2010 in the Bahía de Acapulco (Fig. 1). Two surface samples were collected on 24 July 2010 (Sampling station 1). About 3 liters of seawater were filtered (Whatman GF/F) to determine the presence and the profile of paralytic toxins. Six more seawater samples were collected on 26 July 2010 off Bahía de Acapulco (Sampling stations 2-7) (Fig. 1). Aliquots of 1 mL of these samples were placed in a Sedge-

wick-Rafter chamber under an inverted microscope (Olympus Axiovert 40 C). Images were recorded at 200× with a digital camera (Cannon Power Shot A64Q) and with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Six samples of the violet oyster (*Chama mexicana*; Fig. 2) were collected outside the bay to measure shellfish toxicity. Shellfish toxicity was determined by the standard mouse bioassay method (MBM) and by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-FLD) [3,7,8].

Pyrodinium bahamense var. *compressum* was the species responsible for this bloom (Figs. 3-7). Cell counts are summarized in Table 1. Abundance ranged from 1000 to 606,000 cells L⁻¹; however, densities of 1.462 × 10⁶ cells

Fig. 2. Violet oyster, a sentinel species used to determine shellfish toxicity in Bahía de Acapulco.

Figs. 3-7. Photomicrographs of *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* observed in Bahía de Acapulco, Guerrero, Mexico. Cells observed under light microscope (Figs. 3-4) and scanning electron microscope (Figs. 5-7).

L⁻¹ were found in Bahía de Acapulco [7]. This variety occurred as individual cells and two- and six-cell chains. Cell length ranged from 36 to 49 µm. Shellfish toxicity of violet oyster samples analyzed by mouse bioassay ranged from 893.4–1387.53 µg STXeq 100 g⁻¹ (Table 1).

Analysis of toxicity in oyster samples using HPLC-FLD varied from 579.03–894.56 µgSTXeq 100 g⁻¹ (Table 1). These values are 8–17 times greater than the permitted limit for human consumption. No human poisonings occurred during this event because of the rapid response of the local public health authorities. The toxin profile in the oysters included STX, NeoSTX, GTX3, B1, B2, and C. The toxin profile in phytoplankton included STX, GTX3, B1, B2, and C. STX and NeoSTX were the most important analogue toxins in the oyster samples. Toxin profiles in different marine mollusks included STX, NeoSTX, GTX2, dcSTX, dcGTX2, dcGTX3, and B1 [9]. Variety compressum is highly toxic because its profile is mainly composed of STX, NeoSTX, dcSTX, and B1 [10,11,12] with STX representing up to 85–98 mol% toxin cell⁻¹ [12].

On the Guerrero coast, the first PSP incident during 2010 was observed at Playa el Palmar, Zihuatanejo on 20-21 November. Two people exhibited typical symptoms of PSP toxicity after consuming raw clams and they required hospitalization [13]. On 22 December 2010, there was a new bloom of *P. bahamense* var. *compressum*. After eating raw and cooked clams, 12 people in Zihuatanejo had symptoms of paralytic shellfish poisoning; six required hospitalization. The clam *Donax punctatostriatus* contained 2541µg STXeq 100 g⁻¹ [3]. This level is ~30× above the permitted limit for human consumption. Toxicity of these mollusks was linked to the bloom of *P. bahamense* var. *compressum*. Results from the mouse bioassay and HPLC-FLD methods shown significant differences in total toxicity. Toxicity values calculated by HPLC-FLD seem to be underestimates. Studies to validate the use of methods for analyzing paralytic poisons must be performed. Monitoring of species producing these toxins and toxicity levels in marine mollusks along the coasts of Guerrero is ongoing.

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Table 1. Abundance of *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* and shellfish toxicity in the violet oyster in Bahía de Acapulco.

Sampling stations	<i>P. bahamense</i> var. <i>compressum</i> Cells L ⁻¹	Shellfish toxicity (µg STX / 100 g tissue)	
		MBM	HPLC-FLD
1 (Bahía de Acapulco)	65000-101000	-	-
2 (La Prietilla)	82000	1159.11	781.68
3 (La Palmita)	16000	1236.30	894.57
4 (Punta Pilares)	606000	1387.53	774.22
5 (La Rana)	1000	1179.36	776.76
6 (Caja del Muerto)	83000	820.35	579.03
7 (Punta Bruja)	1000	893.40	683.38

Table 2. Toxin profile in wild *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* samples (ng/filter) and in violet oyster (ng/g) collected in Bahía de Acapulco.

Sampling stations	STX	NeoSTX	GTX 3	B1	B2	C1
Filter 1 - (1)	0,53	-	0,30	0,66	0,24	2,10
Filter 2 - (1)	0,53	-	0,30	2,32	-	0,39
Oyster - (2)	4909,4	94,5	2683,7	10807,0	106,3	28,3
Oyster - (3)	5621,2	108,5	3226,6	10754,2	-	1657,0
Oyster - (4)	4570,0	73,7	2764,9	13133,2	1006,8	40,7
Oyster - (5)	4351,5	146,1	3310,3	10565,3	-	2517,8
Oyster - (6)	2709,2	76,6	2855,0	11461,3	354,4	251,3
Oyster - (7)	3590,5	44,6	3063,2	12106,9	268,4	215,2

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References

- Gárate-Lizárraga I et al. 2008. *Conversus* 9: 22–26
- Gárate-Lizárraga I et al. 2009. *Harmful Algae News* 40: 8–9
- Gárate-Lizárraga I et al. 2011. *CICIMAR Océanides* 25: 67–71
- Licea-Durán S et al. 1999. In: *Tresierra-Aguilar AE & ZG Culquichicón-Malpica (Eds.). VIII Congreso Latinoamericano sobre Ciencias del Mar, 17-21 de octubre de 1999, Trujillo, Perú. pp. 335-337*
- Gárate-Lizárraga I & González-Armas R. 2011. *Mar Poll Bull* 62: 626–630
- Orellana-Cepeda E et al. 2004. In: *Harmful Algae 2002 (9th International Conference)*, pp 514–516
- Díaz-Ortiz JA et al. 2010. *Red Sanitaria* 7: 1–4
- Yu RC et al. 1988. *Chromatographia* 48: 671–676

- Oshima Y 1989. In: *Biology, Epidemiology and Management of Pyrodinium Red Tides (ICLARM, Manila)* pp 1–7
- Núñez-Vázquez EJ et al. 2007. In: *II Taller sobre florecimientos algales nocivos en México. Secretaria de Salud del Estado de Guerrero, p 18*
- Hummert C et al. 1997. *Chromatographia* 45: 312–316
- Gedaria AI et al. 2007. *Toxicon* 50: 518–529
- Mayo-García C 2010. *Despertar de la Costa*, p 29

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First report of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* on Moroccan Atlantic Coast and toxicity in Moroccan shellfish

The diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia* has been recorded along the Mediterranean and Atlantic coasts of Morocco. In the monitoring programme, species identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* is not possible since it requires examination of the fine structure of the cell wall with electron microscopy. The detection and counts of *Pseudo-nitzschia* are reported at generic level [1].

The present work identifies potentially toxic species and confirms the toxicity of the species involved.

Weekly sampling was done on the Atlantic coast: seawater was collected from Oualidia lagoon (32°59'N-08°43'W; 32°58'N-08°45'W), Jemaa Ouled Ghanem area (open sea) (32°51'N-08°53'W; 32°47'N-08°57'W: open sea) and Cap Beddouza (open sea).

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of *Pseudonitzschia* was done from January 2008-December 2009 during the routine HAB monitoring programme. On the Atlantic coast, *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp are frequent components of the phytoplankton (detected in 80%-90% of samples) [2]. *Pseudo-nitzschia* was found in all seasons, in a wide range of temperatures. Highest cell numbers were observed during spring and sum-

mer. The maximum count was 5.4 10⁴ cell L⁻¹, off Cap Beddouza in July 2008, at a temperature of 19°C. In Oualidia lagoon, the *Pseudo-nitzschia* population was composed of large and short chain formers, the former dominant. In the Jemaa Ouled Ghanem area, the large and the short forms were most abundant from April to July 2009.

SEM examination showed one species with large asymmetrical valves, no central interspace (Fig 1.), 7 µm in width; large simple poroids arranged in 2 rows (4 pores in 1µm), 18 interstries in 10µm, and 17 fibules. These characteristics identify it as *P. australis*, a domoic acid producer.

Since 2004, domoic acid was noted in clams and mussels from different shellfish areas located on Atlantic shores, but concentrations rarely reached the legal threshold (20 µg/g of meat) [3]. But in the second week of May 2009, domoic acid in mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from Jemaa Ouled Ghanem shores reached 28.58 µg/g meat, and 43.87 µg/g meat one week later. The shores were closed for harvesting. The phytoplankton analyses revealed high *Pseudo-nitzschia* counts in this period (103 to 104 cell L⁻¹).

This is the first ASP event in Moroc-

can waters with subsequent closure of the areas for harvesting. *Pseudo-nitzschia* is commonly observed in Moroccan Atlantic and Mediteranean waters, and frequently forms blooms in spring and summer. As a DA producer, *Pseudo-nitzschia australis* is implicated in DA accumulation in Moroccan shellfish.

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References

1. Ennaffah B & Chafik A 2007. First HANA Workshop, 7-9 November, Casablanca-Maroc.
2. Ennaffah B 2009. Annual Report of HAB monitoring of shellfish areas, 60pp
3. Taleb H 2009. Annual Report of phyco-toxin monitoring program of shellfish areas, 70pp

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Fig. 1. Scanning electrons micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia australis*. A, B) Valve illustrating asymmetrical valve and absence of central interspace. C) Higher magnification of central part of valves showing the two row of poroids / striae, D)

First report of *Pyrodinium bahamense* in the Straits of Malacca

Pyrodinium bahamense is the main causative organism responsible for paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) events in Malaysia. The species was first found on the Sabah Bornean coast in 1970 [1]. No record of *P. bahamense* was reported from other parts of Malaysian waters thus far. The distribution of this dinoflagellate is generally presumed to be confined only to Sabah waters. In our recent plankton survey at Port Dickson, the Strait of Malacca (Fig. 1), we found cells that resembled *Pyrodinium* in the plankton samples. Cells appeared as two-cell chains in very low densities in net samples. Based on the morphological characteristics of the cells, the

Fig. 2. *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* from Port Dickson, Malaysia. LM showing 2 cells in chain.

Fig. 1. Malaysian map showing the sampling sites.

species was confirmed as *P. bahamense* var. *compressum* (Fig. 2). This is the first record of *P. bahamense* from the Strait of Malacca. The question arose as to whether the species has been overlooked in previous plankton studies or has been introduced by human activity, such as ballast water discharge. This could only be answered with more studies and information obtained on the natural and cultured specimens from Port Dickson.

Alexandrium tamiyavanichii is another highly toxic dinoflagellate responsible for PSP in Malaysia [2]. In Malaysia, the distribution of this species has been confirmed in Sebatu, Melacca (Lim, 1999) [3] and Kota Kinabalu, Sabah [4]. Most recently, the species was encountered in the waters of Sarawak. A clonal culture of *A. tamiyavanichii* was established from the estuary of Samariang, Sarawak. Thecal plate

arrangement of cultured cells stained with Calcofluor White was observed by fluorescence microscopy. Based on features of apical pore complex (APC), anterior sulcal plate (s.a.) and posterior sulcal plate (s.p.), the strain was identified as *A. tamiyavanichii*. Toxicity of this strain was further confirmed by ELISA (Skit, Shin Nihon Kentei Kyokai, Japan) and HPLC [5].

The findings of *P. bahamense* from Port Dickson and *A. tamiyavanichii* from Samariang have shown the need to expand monitoring of these species in our waters. Plankton monitoring and toxicity tests on edible molluscs from the areas should be carried out to ensure they are safe for local consumption.

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References

1. Roy RN 1977. *Medical Journal of Malaysia* 31: 247-251
2. Lim PT et al 2006. *J Phycol* 42: 786-799
3. Lim PT 1999. *Msc Thesis, UKM*.
4. Adam A et al 2011. *Harmful Algae* 10: 495-502
5. Usup G et al 2002. *Harmful Algae* 1: 265-275

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Fig. 3. *Alexandrium tamiyavanichii* from Samariang, Sarawak, Malaysia. Epi-fluorescence micrograph with four cells in chain (a) and the apical view (b).

Monitoring potentially ichthyotoxic phytoflagellates in southern fjords of Chile

Autotrophic phytoflagellates have been poorly studied in Chilean coastal waters [1]. These cells are extremely fragile, and are not usually identifiable in preserved samples [2]. *Heterosigma akashiwo* and *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa* are two species of ichthyotoxic flagellates that have generated significant losses to the salmon industry in southern Chilean fjords. *P. cf. verruculosa* was initially classified as a raphidophyte (as *Chattonella verruculosa*), but DNA sequencing places the species in the Dictyochophyceae [3, 4]. These independent studies renamed it *Pseudochattonella verruculosa* and *Verrucophora verruculosa* respectively. The first of these names currently has priority.

Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa was first detected by the monitoring program in the Cholgo area (Hornopirén) during summer 2004. In that year, it occurred in Reloncaví Fjord and Sound, Calbuco, North and Central-South Chiloé Island and Quintupeu fjord (Fig. 1B). In this last place, the greatest abundance was 22 cells ml⁻¹, a concentration sufficient to produce farmed salmon mortalities that ranged between 2 and 5%, with a diagnosis that reported neurological and digestive problems. This event coincided with a high sea surface temperature and an intense outbreak of *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. Subsequently, the pres-

ence of this dictyophyte has recurred in the summer months of January and February in the years 2005, 2009 and 2011 (Fig. 2A). These last two blooms have been the most important in terms of cell abundance, reaching concentrations of 394 and 42 cells ml⁻¹ in the areas of Huenquillahue and Cabras Island respectively, and comprising up to 75% of the total phytoplankton community (Fig. 2C).

In the spring of 1988, particularly in September, the salmon industry experienced a major crisis due to an intense outbreak of the ichthyotoxic raphidophyte *H. akashiwo*, which was colloquially called "brown tide". Because of high

concentrations of this species, greater than 100,000 cells ml⁻¹, there was high mortality of farmed salmon in the inner sea of Los Lagos region (Reloncaví sound, Hornopirén and Chiloé Island). Associated mortalities were higher than 5000 tons and economic losses about US\$11 M. Due to this event, the phytoplankton monitoring program was set up, covering a great part of the northern Patagonian inner sea. This program began to detect the presence of *H. akashiwo* again in 1993 and 1994 (Fig. 2B). In these years (from September to December and January to March, respectively), the maximum concentration was 18 cells ml⁻¹ and its distribu-

Fig. 1. A) Study area in southern Chile. B) Detection zones of *P. cf. verruculosa* and *H. akashiwo*.

Fig. 2. A-B) Temporal variation in abundance of *P. cf. verruculosa* and *H. akashiwo* (cells ml⁻¹). C-D) Temporal variation in ichthyotoxic phytoflagellates/total phytoplankton (cells ml⁻¹) ratio.

Fig. 3. T-S diagram showing water masses in which ichthyotoxic phytoflagellates were detected.

Fig. 4. A-F) Morphological variations of *Pseudochattonella cf. verruculosa* in southern fjords of Chile. Scale bar: 10µm.

Fig. 5. A. *Heterosigma akashiwo* vegetative cell. B-E. *H. akashiwo*. Cell destruction sequence due to Lugol fixation. Scale bar: 10µm.

tion was restricted to areas of Hornopirén, Reloncaví Sound and Calbuco in 1993, and in 1994 reached the coast of Chiloé. In 2000 an event of great magnitude was recorded again, especially in the Reñihue fjord, associated with mortalities of up to 40% of caged salmon with low abundance of 40 cells ml⁻¹, which corroborates the high toxicity of this species for these fish. *H. akashiwo* impacted farmed salmon during March 2002 on the coast of Quemchi, and more recently in 2011 in association with *P. cf. verruculosa*.

Both species, *H. akashiwo* and *P. cf. verruculosa*, have been detected in similar ecological niches, primarily in estuarine waters. TS diagrams show these phytoflagellates associated with water temperatures between 11.2 and 17.3 °C (*H. akashiwo*) and between 10 and 18.5 °C (*P. cf. verruculosa*), which describes their appearance in the fjord during spring and summer (Fig. 3). Blooms of these species have been observed in stratified waters with salinities between 11.4 and 33.3 psu, but their greatest abundance has been near 25 psu. Both *P. cf. verruculosa* and *H. akashiwo* are difficult to identify with light microscopy, mainly due to their high morphological variability (Fig. 4) and their lability in fixing solutions (Fig. 5). There is no information to show these phytoflagellates have been introduced to Chilean waters through ballast water, but their presence has only been recorded since the beginning salmon farming in southern Chilean fjords.

References

1. Parra O et al 1991. *Gayana Botánica* 48: 101-110
2. Jeffrey, S. W. & M. Vesk, 1997. In: *Phytoplankton Pigments in Oceanography: Guidelines to Modern Methods (Monographs on Oceanographic Methodology. SCOR-UNESCO)*, pp 37-84
3. Hosoi-Tanabe S et al 2007. *Phycological Research* 55: 185-192
4. Edvardsen B et al 2007. *Journal of Phycology* 43: 1054-1070

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First record of the ciguatera causing genus *Gambierdiscus* in Brazil

Gambierdiscus was recorded for the first time in Brazil in March 2006 associated with macroalgae *Tricleocarpa cylindrica*, *Ulva lactuca* and *Caulerpa sertularioides* collected from Maracaípe, Pernambuco state (8° 32' S, 35° 00' W), northeast Brazil. *Gambierdiscus* sp. was present in low numbers (respectively 29, 10 and 17 cells g fresh weight macroalgae-1) and was accompanied by *Prorocentrum lima* (the most abundant species in the epi-benthic dinoflagellate community of those samples), *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata*, *Prorocentrum rhathymum*, *Prorocentrum emarginatum*, *Amphidinium* sp. and *Coolia* sp. [1]. The area is a shallow reef close to a small river discharge that drains a mangrove. Mean annual seawater temperature is 26 °C and varies between 25 °C and 28 °C. Studies on the *Gambierdiscus* specimens from northeastern Brazil are being conducted.

More recently, in 2007, *Gambierdiscus* was also found in macroalgae samples from Rio de Janeiro, at Armação dos Búzios (22° 45' S, 41° 53' W) and Arraial do Cabo (22° 59' S, 42° 00' W, Fig. 1) [2]. In Rio de Janeiro, epi-benthic dinoflagellates were monitored from June 2006 to November 2007. *Gambierdiscus* sp. was recorded for the first time in this region in March 2007. A total of 276 macroalgae samples were collected and analysed during that study from two stations: Forno embayment (Arraial do Cabo) and Tartaruga (Armação dos Búzios) and the genus *Gambierdiscus* was present in 20% of samples.

The genus was found associated with macroalgae *Sargassum vulgare*, *Padina gymnospora*, *Canistrocarpus cervicornis*, *Caulerpa racemosa*, *Amphiroa fragilissima*, *A. brasiliana*, *Codium intertextum* and *Hypnea musciformis*. However, only in *Sargassum vulgare* and *Hypnea musciformis* samples from Tartaruga, did *Gambierdiscus* exceed an abundance of 10 cells g FW⁻¹. It was more frequently found associated with *Sargassum vulgare*, and was present in 40% of the 52 *Sargassum vulgare* samples analysed from Tartaruga station.

The highest *Gambierdiscus* cell density found in the area was 74 cells g *Sargassum vulgare* FW⁻¹ in April 2007, when *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* was the most abundant species (238 *O. cf. ovata* cells.g FW⁻¹). In May 2007, low total epi-benthic dinoflagellate densities (71 dinoflagellate cells g *S. vulgare* FW⁻¹) were observed, and *Gambierdiscus* was the more abundant epi-benthic dinoflagellate, with mean abundance of 37 cells g *S. vulgare* FW⁻¹. Surface water temperature at Tartaruga varies between 20 and 25 °C while at Arraial do Cabo temperature ranges from 16 to 24 °C, due to coastal upwelling.

The study area fits well the permissive habitats reported for the genus, including annual water temperature between 21 and 31 °C, abundant macroalgae or other substrata for the cells to attach to, low to moderate turbulence, high, stable salinities and attenuated light levels [3]. It is likely that the increased cell numbers recorded at Tar-

Fig. 1. Map of Brazil showing the three locations where the genus *Gambierdiscus* was reported.

taruga, relative to Forno, may be related to consistently higher temperatures at the former station, due to the influence of coastal upwelling at Forno. However, this assumption requires further studies.

Gambierdiscus specimens from Rio de Janeiro are in agreement with the morphological description of *G. excentricus* recently described in samples from the Canary Islands [4]. The cells are lenticular, anteroposteriorly compressed, round to ellipsoid in apical and antapical view with numerous golden-brown chloroplasts disposed radially (Fig. 2a). The average depth (dorsoventral diameter) of cells is 98 ± 6 (88-107) μm and width 80 ± 5 (72-88) μm (n=27). The thecal surface has nu-

Fig. 2. *Gambierdiscus excentricus* from Armação dos Búzios, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. a) Light microscopy of cell in apical view. b) Part of the epitheca showing the diagnostic 2' plate in light microscopy. c) SEM image of the hypotheca.

merous irregularly distributed round pores (Fig. 2a,b). The apical pore plate (Po) is oval and ventrally displaced and the second apical plate 2' has the suture 2'/3' about twice as long as the suture 2'/4' (Fig. 2b); plate 6'' was not observed. Plate 2'''' is about twice as long as wide, being wider towards the ventral side (Fig 2c).

Although in low abundance, the presence of the genus raises concerns regarding the occurrence of ciguatera. Brazil has an extensive coast and experiences prolonged elevated water temperatures. This condition is favorable for increased *Gambierdiscus* growth, and often correlates with increased incidence of ciguatera [3]. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a monitoring programme for the genus and broaden

our knowledge of the geographical distribution of *Gambierdiscus*. There are no official reports of ciguatera in Brazil. However, in some areas of the northeast coast, local communities avoid the consumption of top predator fish of the Lutjanidae during a few months each year, and there have been anecdotal reports of domestic animals intoxicated after eating fish viscera. The possible relations between these observations and ciguatera toxins need further investigation.

References

1. Nascimento SM 2006. 12th International Conference on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen, 248
2. Nascimento SM et al 2010. Epi-benthic dinoflagellates from the Rio de Janeiro

coastline, Brazil. GEOHAB OSM on Benthic HABs, Honolulu, Hawaii

3. Litaker RW et al 2010. *Toxicon* 56: 711-730
4. Fraga S et al 2011. *Harmful Algae*

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15th ICHA 2012 Korea

15차 국제 적조 회의
XV International Conference on Harmful Algae

Korea XV ICHA 2012

Dear HABs friends and colleagues all over the world!

It is my great pleasure to invite you to Korea to join the 15th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) from 29 October - 2 November 2012 at the Changwon Exhibition Conference Center (CECO), Gyeongnam, Republic of Korea, under the theme of "Man and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)".

The purpose of this meeting is to share new international findings on HABs and to provide an exciting opportunity to celebrate the power of our collaborative research. We will do our best to make the 15th ICHA meeting one of the most informative and interesting international HABs conferences.

I kindly ask you, our HABs friends and colleagues, to join this meeting and also to enjoy the excitement and dynamics of Korean life. In the fall of 2012, the colorful mountains and productive coastlines will be ready to welcome your visit to "Korea XV ICHA2012."

The Conference will address the following topics of interest:

- Population dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms
- Time series of HAB events: Climatic and anthropogenic induced impacts
- Impact of HABs on marine food webs and ecosystem structure and function
- Biological interactions: allelopathy, mixotrophy, parasitism, symbiosis, bacteria and viruses
- New regional HAB events
- Inland Seas and HABs
- Introduction of alien species and HABs
- Cyanobacterial ecology, physiology and bioactive compounds
- Genomics and genetic diversity of HABs
- Toxins: chemical structure and synthesis, detection and analytical methods
- Novel sensor technologies for bio-sensing applications in HAB research and monitoring.
- Harmful Algae culture collections
- Management, mitigation and public outreach for HABs

Kim Du Kwan
Governor of
Gyeongsangnam-do

Kim Young Man
President of NFRDI

Han Myung Soo
Chair of KORHAB

Kim Hak Gyoon
Chair of Local
Organizing Committee,
15th ICHA

Two new localities for *Gambierdiscus toxicus* in the Mexican Pacific

Fig. 1. Global distribution of *Gambierdiscus toxicus*. The black triangles are the new locations.

Gambierdiscus toxicus was described 32 years ago and since then its overall distribution has always been referred to as epiphytic and benthic in circumtropical reefs. It was first described in the Tuamotu Archipelago and the Gambier Islands [1], hence its name in French Polynesia. It was discovered almost simultaneously in Hawaii [2], then in the Indian Ocean [3], in the Virgin Islands and Florida [4], Belize, Caribbean [5], mostly in Cuba where it represents just over 50% [6], and on the Great Barrier Reef [7]. In the Gulf of Mexico it has been recorded only off the coasts of Quintana Roo [8], Yucatan [9] and in Veracruz [10]. In the Gulf of California it is known from La Paz and Magdalena bays [11] (Fig. 1).

On 25 February 2011, as part of a project “Reproductive biology of coral-destroying sponges” (SEP-CONACYT: 102 239), samples were collected with a 60 micron mesh horizontal plankton sampler [12] around Isabel Island (30 km off the coast of Nayarit) and the largest island of the Revillagigedo Archipelago, Socorro Island (Fig. 2). Large amounts of “smallest discus” were tak-

Fig. 2. Location of Isabel and Socorro Islands, Mexican Pacific. Red triangles are sampling sites.

en, later identified as *Gambierdiscus toxicus* Adachi et Fukuyo, 1979 [1]. Close examination of selected specimens with a scanning electron microscope indicate an almost exact coincidence of this material with the morphological characteristics previously described by Okolodkov (Table 1). Only the length of the apical pore complex (APC) was greater [8], and the hook-shaped opening of the specimens from Socorro Island was occluded by a membrane (Fig. 3B). In the Mexican Pacific, there is evidence of ciguatera in La Paz and Magdalena bays and in Alijos Rock and Pardito Island and it has been suspected that this ciguatera is due to *G. toxicus* and *Ostreopsis ovata* [13]. However, until now, there were no firm identifications. This study confirms the presence of *Gambierdiscus toxicus*. There is still no evidence of *O. ovata*, but *Ostreopsis siamensis* has been identified on Isabel Island [14].

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References

1. Adachi R & Fukuyo Y 1979. *Bull Jpn Soc Sci Fish* 45:67-71
2. Taylor DL & Seliger H 1979. *Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms* (Elsevier), pp71-76
3. Carlson RD & Tindall DR 1985. *Toxic Dinoflagellates* (Elsevier), pp171-176
4. Quod JL 1994. *Rev Cryptogamie Algol* 15: 243-251
5. Faust M 1995. *J Phycol* 31: 996-1006
6. Delgado G et al 2006. *Rev Biol Trop* 52: 299-310
7. Gillespie NC et al 1986. *Med J Austr* 145: 584-590
8. Hernandez BDU & Almazan B 2004. *Rev Biol Trop* 52 (suppl 1): 77-87
9. Okolodkov YB et al. 2009. *HAN* 40: 12-14
10. Okolodkov YB et al 2007. *Aquat Microb Ecol* 47: 223-237
11. Okolodkov YB et al 2006. *Acta Botanica Mexicana* 74: 55pp
12. Rützler K et al 1980. *Mar Ecol* 1: 65-71
13. Sierra B et al. 1998. *Toxicon* 36: 1493-1502
14. Cortés-Lara MC et al. 2005. *HAN* 28: 4-5

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Table 1. Morphology of *Gambierdiscus toxicus* in Yucatan and the Mexican Pacific.

Character (µm)	Okolodkov et al 2009	I. Isabel	I. Socorro
Form	lenticulate	=	=
Transdiameter	65-95	76-91.4	97
Long D-V	52.5-70	72-83	94
Long A-Antapical	63-87.5	41.6-50	?
Long APC	6.23-8.6	8-9	8.06
Wide APC	4.56-5.38	5.23-6.25	4.35
Form APC	ellipsoidal_fishhook	=	to cover
Pore APC	48	45-54	45
Cingulum	Ascends	=	=
List	Smooth	=	=
No.plates	8	=	=
Pore plates Ø	0.4	0.2-0.3	0.4

Fig. 3. *Gambierdiscus toxicus*: a-b Socorro Island. c-d Isabel Island. a) apical view. b) APC occluded. c) side view. d) APC open.

First bloom of *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata* in the continental Portuguese coast

Fig. 1. Sampling site on Lagos beach

Blooms of *Ostreopsis* in coastal areas are a topic of increasing interest, mainly in the Mediterranean area, due to the potential hazard that species of this genus might cause to human health and the consequent negative effect on the tourism economy. In contrast to typical blooms of other planktonic dinoflagellates, *Ostreopsis*, as an epibenthic genus, proliferates to form a thin pellicle that covers the substrate. Cell aggregates are normally released into the water column after events of increasing hydrodynamism (waves, tides). These aggregates are detectable by sight as mucilaginous flocs in the water column and at surface in shallow waters.

During the last decade, records of *Ostreopsis* events have been increasing in the Mediterranean. Following outbreaks in the W Mediterranean, in the Balearic Islands in 2005 and on the Murcia coast of Spain in 2006, *Ostreopsis* spp were detected in the NE Atlantic, in macroalgae samples from Madeira and the Canary Islands [1]. The species was later identified as *O. cf. ovata* [2]. On the Moroccan Atlantic coast off Cape Ghir, *O. cf. siamensis* was observed for the first time in 2004 and blooms have been increasing in intensity and frequency since then [3]. In 2008, sev-

eral fishermen from the Portuguese Selvagens Islands (located at the same latitude as Cape Ghir) became sick after eating a fish from the genus *Seriola*. The phytoplankton community present in seawater samples from those islands and provided to the IPIMAR monitoring programme revealed the presence of *Ostreopsis* spp., although the relationship with the syndrome was not established. On the Portuguese mainland, during 2008, *Ostreopsis* cf. *siamensis* was identified for the first time in the SW upwelling coast of Sines [4]. In the same year, this species was detected in

the Portuguese mid-Atlantic Azores Archipelago together with *O. heptagona* and *O. cf. ovata* [5].

In September 2011, as part of a sampling program started in 2010 [6], a bloom of *Ostreopsis* was seen on the beach of D. Ana (Lagos coast, south Portugal, Fig. 1) due to the presence of mucilaginous filaments. This information was communicated to IPIMAR, the national phytoplankton monitoring laboratory, which intensified sampling in time and in adjacent areas. The bloom reached densities as high as 5420 cells L⁻¹ although concentrations were lower (40 to 320 cells L⁻¹) in adjacent areas. A forecast of bloom transport and aggregation/dispersion was made with the MOHID operational model for the Portuguese coast (<http://forecast.maretec.org/>), under the framework of FP7-ASIMUTH project (IST-IPIMAR). Local authorities closed several beaches for bathing once informed about the bloom occurrence and model predictions for its transport.

Identification of *Ostreopsis* solely on morphological criteria is difficult, even when details of the thecal plates are taken into account. As in most *Ostreopsis* blooms, there was great morphological and size variability in cells from the Lagos coast. Cell dimensions fell within the range of *O. cf. siamensis* and *O. cf. ovata* and were smaller than the other described *Ostreopsis* species (Figs. 2 and 3). Due to the difficulty of finding a conclusive morphological identification, a genetic analysis was performed to both field and cultured strains based on the ITS1-5.8S-ITS2. Genetic analyses revealed the presence of *Ostreopsis* cf. *ovata*. Our sequences, when compared

Fig. 2. Calcofluor stained field cells of *Ostreopsis*. Hypotheca (a) and epitheca (b) views

Fig. 3. Field sample of *Ostreopsis*: (a) Light microscopy; (b) Calcofluor stained specimens showing morphological variability.

to the ones of GenBank showed high similarity (99%) with strains from the Mediterranean Sea (e. g. Aegean Sea, Catalan Coast, and Tyrrhenian Sea) [2].

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References

1. Fraga S et al 2005. Poster, ASLO Summer 2005 (Santiago Compostela, Spain)
2. Penna et al 2010. *J Biogeography* 37: 830-841
3. Bennouna et al 2010. *HAN* 42:1 & 3
4. Amorim et al 2010. *HAN* 42: 6-7
5. Silva et al 2010. *HAN* 42: 1-2
6. David H et al., 2011. *ICOD proceedings*, 4-8 April (Villefranche-sur-mer)

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IOC WESTPAC Training course on Taxonomy and Ecology of the diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*

A UNESCO IOC/WESTPAC training course with the theme: 'Taxonomy and Ecology of the Diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*' was held 20-24 March 2011 at the Faculty of Resource Science and Technology, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Kota Samarahan, Malaysia. The event was jointly organized by UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission

sub-commission for the Western Pacific (IOC WESTPAC) and the Asian Natural Environmental Science Center, University of Tokyo, with distinguished speakers from Japan, Denmark and Vietnam.

The training course drew participants from seven countries (China, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam), including rep-

resentatives from government agencies and research institutions.

During the course, participants were given hands-on training in basic and advanced techniques in *Pseudo-nitzschia* identification. These included scanning and transmission electron microscopy, and rapid molecular detection techniques using fluorescence in situ hybridization. A series of lectures was also delivered in the four-day course by Dr Nina Lundholm.

A Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) Seminar was conducted in conjunction with the course. Nearly 90 participants attended the seminar. The talks were given by Drs Yasuwo Fukuyo, Nina Lundholm and Ha Dao Viet.

Dr Yasuwo Fukuyo, the first vice chair of the IOC/WESTPAC, and the leader of WESTPAC HAB Project have emphasized the importance of HAB research in the region. HAB events have been increasingly reported globally, and cause poisoning and fatalities due to consumption of toxic shellfish, including Malaysia. Besides causing harm to the environment, plants, and animals, these blooms can be detrimental to aquaculture, fisheries, and coastal tourism, as well as the health of local communities. According to the organising chairperson, Dr Po-Teen Lim, such a training course is timely and vital to strengthen the regional network and collaboration in HABs research. It is crucial in standardizing scientific approaches used in identification of the diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia*, and most importantly to enhance human capital to deal with HABs issues, especially in the national and international agencies.

Fig. 1. More than 90 participants during the Harmful Algal Bloom Seminar.

Fig. 2. Dr Lim explained on SEM during the hand-on session.

Fig. 3. Dr Ha from Institute of Oceanography, Vietnam talks during the Harmful Algal Bloom Seminar

Fig. 4. Dr Lundholm demonstrates acid wash preparation to participants

Application of a Receptor Binding Assay to the analyses of PSP toxins in four species of shellfish in El Salvador

Harmful algal blooms of paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) toxin producers have a serious impact on public health and cause millionaire losses to the shellfish industry on the Pacific coast of El Salvador [1]. In 2010 and 2011, high levels of PSP toxins associated with a bloom of *Pyrodinium bahamense* var. *compressum* were detected in several mollusc species and led to shellfish harvesting closures. Recently, the Marine Toxins Laboratory, University of El Salvador (LABTOX-UES), has implemented a receptor-binding assay (RBA) method [2] for the detection of PSP toxins in shellfish. The RBA method is currently used in laboratories around the world

homogenizing 1-2 g of flesh that was extracted with an equivalent volume of HCl 0.1N. The pH of the extract was measured and corrected (if needed), to get a value between 3.0 and 4.0. This extract was boiled for 5 min, cooled to room temperature, centrifuged (3400 x g) and the supernatant collected and filtered with a syringe (0.45 µm).

The RBA Method: The acidic shellfish extracts were analyzed according to the STX receptor-binding assay. The method is based on the specific interaction between the toxins and their pharmacological target, i.e. the voltage-gated sodium channel, site 1 for PSP toxins. In this assay, a radio-labelled toxin [³H]

Results

Saxitoxin-like activity was detected in all samples analyzed. Detection limits of the assay were about 7.6 µg equiv. STX/100 g meat. Samples were diluted, as needed, whenever their concentration of PSP toxins exceeded the linear range of the calibration curve. Similar results were obtained from samples where different dilution factors were used. Concentrations above 2500 µg quiv. STX/100 g meat were detected in oysters and crabs in September 2011 (Fig. 1). Thus, the RBA can analyze samples with toxin levels providing an adequate dilution factor is selected.

Acknowledgements

To IAEA, project *Detection of Marine Toxins through the Use of the Radioassay Method in El Salvador* for its valuable support to set up the LABTOX-UES laboratory and to the National Oceanic and

Table 1. Concentrations of PSP toxins (µg STX equiv./ 100 g meat) detected with the RBA. A regulatory level of 80 µg equiv. STX/100 g meat (400 mouse units) is applied in El Salvador.

LABTOX Reference	Sampling site	Sample	Shellfish	Date of analysis (dd/mm/yy)	STX (µg equiv/100g)	Mouse Units
MIZ21-24	Mizata Beach	whole tissue	oysters	12/09/11	145.3	727
MIZ26-28	Mizata Beach	whole tissue	oysters	29/09/11	731.4	3657
TAQ01-03	Taquillo Beach	whole tissue	oysters	25/08/11	1872.4	9362
CUC01-03	El Cuco Beach	whole tissue	oysters	31/08/11	138.7	694
MIZ31-32	Mizata Beach	whole tissue	snails	11/10/11	1622	8110
MIZ33-34	Mizata Beach	whole tissue	oysters	11/10/11	2809	14040
MIZ37-38	Mizata Beach	whole tissue	mussels	11/10/11	771.2	3856
ZON01-03	El Zonte Beach	whole tissue	snails	01/10/11	463.2	2316
ZON04-06	El Zonte Beach	whole tissue	crabs	01/10/11	2604	13020

as a fast and sensitive alternative to the mouse bioassay. This receptor binding assay for PSP toxins has been evaluated in an AOAC Single Laboratory Validation [3] and has just been approved as an official analytical procedure following AOAC interlaboratory trials. LABTOX-UES, in cooperation with NOAA, had previously used the RBA to determine PSP toxins in sea turtles. The RBA has allowed early warning of the presence of PSP toxins in shellfish in El Salvador, and probably contributed to save human lives.

Material and Methods

Samples of oysters (*Crassostrea iridiscens*), snails (*Plicopurpura columellaris*), crabs (*Carcinus maenas*) and mussels (*Modiolus capax*) were prepared by

saxitoxin) competes with unlabeled molecules for the sodium channel sites in a rat-brain crude membrane preparation. When the binding equilibrium is reached, free [³H]toxins are removed by filtration and collected receptor-bound [³H]toxins are quantified by liquid scintillation counting. The reduction in [³H] toxin binding is directly proportional to the amount of unlabelled toxin present. A standard curve is generated using increasing concentrations of unlabeled toxin standard; the concentration of toxin in extracts of samples is determined with reference to the standard curve. Thus, the RBA is a functional assay that estimates the toxic potential (toxicity) of the extract, in a manner comparable to the mouse bioassay.

Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) for their cooperation and technical assistance.

References

- 1 Barraza J 2009. *Toxicon* 54: 895-896
- 2 Powell C et al 1999. *Natural Toxins* 7: 393-400
- 3 Van Dolah F et al 2009. *Journal of AOAC International* 92: 1705-1713

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First report of *Dinophysis* species causing Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning in British Columbia, Canada

Fig. 1. Map of Vancouver Island and south coast of BC, showing HAMP sampling site (Conville Bay) and DSP-affected mussel harvest site (Gorge Harbour).

The western province of Canada, British Columbia (BC), has a temperate climate and naturally nutrient rich coastal water with high primary productivity. Historically, BC has been one of the areas most affected by harmful algal blooms (HABs), including those of algae species that cause shellfish poisoning syndromes. Routine monitoring of shellfish for the presence of Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (PSP) toxins in BC began in 1942, following a severe outbreak of PSP with six deaths recorded [1]. Cases of Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) have not been recorded in BC; however the ASP toxin, domoic acid (DA), has been found in shellfish [2]. Currently, BC shellfish are tested by the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) for the presence of PSP toxins weekly in summer and bi-weekly in winter. Occasion-

ally these samples are also tested for DA.

The first case of Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (DSP) on the west coast of Canada was announced by the CFIA in August 2011. Approximately 60 people became sick from consuming mussels harvested in Gorge Harbour, Cortes Island, between July 19 and August 2, 2011 [3]. After the poisoning outbreak, the CFIA recalled the affected product and issued an official warning to the public not to consume these mussels.

DSP has caused significant problems in other parts of the world, especially in Europe, and presently many countries rely on a combination of phytoplankton sampling and shellfish toxicity monitoring. The early warning level of DSP-causing *Dinophysis* species in water samples that triggers further testing of

shellfish flesh for DSP toxins depends on the region, but in most countries is in the range of 100-500 cells L⁻¹.

Species of *Dinophysis* (especially *D. acuminata*, *D. norvegica*, and *D. fortii*) are very common in BC coastal waters. A two-year study in the 1990s [4] revealed the presence of *Dinophysis* species with concentrations above known DSP-causing levels throughout the sampling area [4]. Another study pointed out that the absence of diagnosed DSP in humans in BC at the time might be due to the fact that diarrhoea, the major DSP symptom, resembles bacterial contamination, so DSP could not be detected without testing specifically for toxins [5]. The absence of early warning due to insufficient testing for DSP toxins and lack of monitoring of shellfish HAB species eventually led to this year's outbreak. Currently, there is no phytoplankton monitoring in BC by government agencies: neither the federal departments of the CFIA and Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO), nor provincial or municipal organizations.

As well as threatening human health by causing shellfish toxicity, HABs are a major economic threat to the BC salmon aquaculture industry. Algal blooms in BC are not known to cause a health risk to fish consumers, but HABs are the primary health issue of farmed salmon in BC due to frequent fish kills at farm sites. Striving for efficient HAB management and mitigation, a consortium of BC fish farmers, in association with DFO, initiated the Harmful Algae Monitoring Program (HAMP) in 1999. Since that time HAMP personnel have analysed weekly samples from 1, 5, and 10 m depths at sampling sites on or near fish farms for the presence of harmful algae, which has resulted in warnings of potentially harmful events.

Dinophysis species are not harmful to fish and thus their concentrations are not usually enumerated during HAMP sample analysis. However, in June 2011 the concentrations of *Dinophysis* at a few sampling sites appeared much higher than usual, so HAMP staff started counting *Dinophysis* in these areas. This included one HAMP sampling

Fig. 2. *Dinophysis* species count, Conville Bay, BC, 2011.

site – Conville Bay – which was about 25 km from the area where mussels were later affected by DSP biotoxin (Fig. 1). The highest concentration of *Dinophysis* species recorded at this site was 24000 cell L⁻¹ on July 20 at 5 m depth (Fig. 2). The most common species observed in the samples at this site were: *D. acuminata*, *D. acuta*, *D. fortii* and *D. rotundata* (Fig. 3). The most abundant species was *D. acuminata*; from July 13 to August 17 it comprised 82% of the total *Dinophysis* count (Fig. 4). The highest concentrations of *Dinophysis*, in terms of depth, were usually recorded at 5 m (Fig. 5); for the period of July 13 to August 20 the count for *D. acuminata* on average was 6800 cells L⁻¹ at 5 m, and 4000 and 3300 cells L⁻¹ at 1 m and 10 m respectively.

The unusually high concentrations of *Dinophysis* in Conville Bay coincided with the Gorge Harbour DSP event. Based on available phytoplankton data and results of CFIA DSP toxin analysis, it appears that DSP toxin exceeded the regulatory limit on July 19th, around the time of highest *Dinophysis* concentrations, throughout the monitored water column in Conville Bay (July 20th: 12000 cells L⁻¹ at 1 m, 24000 cells L⁻¹ at 5 m, and 13000 cells L⁻¹ at 10 m). About two weeks after the highest *Dinophysis* concentrations, the level of DSP toxins returned to acceptable levels in Gorge Harbour shellfish samples.

This DSP outbreak in BC highlights the necessity of monitoring and studying algal species known to produce shellfish toxins. The prevention of

Fig. 3. Most common *Dinophysis* species in Conville Bay July 13 - August 17, 2011. a) *D. acuminata*, b) *D. acuta*, c) *D. fortii*, and d) *D. rotundata*

Fig. 4. Percentages of *D. acuminata*, *D. acuta*, *D. fortii*, and *D. rotundata* in Conville Bay samples from July 13 to August 17, 2011.

Fig. 5. Average concentrations of *D. acuminata* at 1, 5, and 10 m depths from July 13 to August 17, 2011 at Conville Bay.

shellfish borne illnesses requires not only monitoring of shellfish flesh for the presence of toxins but also analysis of water samples for the presence of harmful algae. Data on the occurrence, type and concentrations of toxic algae provides an early warning of toxic events: which toxin may be expected to be found in shellfish, and when to monitor product for toxins. Knowledge of the local phytoplankton population, ecology of the toxic species, and detecting harmful algal blooms helps to prevent poisoning cases and protect shellfish consumers.

- Canadian Food Inspection Agency 2011 <http://www.inspection.gc.ca/english/corpaffr/rearapp/2011/20110806e.shtml>
- Taylor FJR et al 1994. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 103: 151-264
- Taylor FJR & Harrison PJ 2002. *PICES Scientific Report* 23: 77-88

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References

- Quayle DB 1969. *Bulletin of the Fisheries Research Board of Canada*, 168, 68 pp
- Marine Biotoxins* 2004. *FAO Food and Nutrition Paper* 80 <http://www.fao.org/docrep/007/y5486e/y5486e00.htm>

Harmful Algal Bloom Operational Forecast System in the US

A Need Realized

It was October 31, 1987—Halloween Day in the U.S. It seemed to be an otherwise ordinary day, but people on the beaches near Beaufort, North Carolina, were experiencing out of the ordinary respiratory distress. A bloom of “Florida red tide”, the toxic algae *Karenia brevis*, had unexpectedly appeared in North Carolina coastal waters for the first time on record. It stayed for almost half of a year.

This persistent and unforeseen harmful algal bloom (HAB) was economically disastrous for shellfisheries, seafood, and tourism, costing an estimated \$25 million to North Carolina coastal communities (about \$47 million today). A need to better monitor, predict, and plan for events like this—integrating all available data from satellites, field monitoring, and ultimately models—was clear.

The bloom had been transported from Florida via the warm waters of the Gulf Stream. During the event, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration’s (NOAA’s) polar orbiting environmental satellites were able to collect data that allowed scientists to detect ocean thermal features associated with the bloom and provided a means for tracking it. Before that time, high resolution images of sea surface temperature were not routinely available to coastal managers. This red tide event illustrated the need for near real-time satellite data and gave birth to NOAA’s CoastWatch Program. By 1989, NOAA was processing the full resolution satellite imagery on an operational basis and distributing it within a day to the coastal management community.

HAB Forecasting Today

The world of HAB monitoring and forecasting in the U.S. has come a long way since 1987. Since 2004, NOAA, in collaboration with many entities, has been developing and successfully transitioning operational forecasts for HABs that integrate data from satellites and field monitoring with models. (<http://www.tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/hab>).

The first operational HAB forecasts in the US were introduced for the eastern Gulf of Mexico (Florida). To this

day, operational HAB forecast bulletins, providing *K. brevis* detection and forecast information, are distributed twice weekly to managers during blooms and once weekly during non-bloom periods, with daily beach conditions available to the public via the Web and phone hotlines. The nowcasts and forecasts in the eastern Gulf of Mexico are based on a combination of 1) biological, oceanographic, and meteorological field data from federal, state, and local agencies, 2) satellite imagery, 3) public and animal health reports from state and local agencies, and 4) transport models. The bulletins allow for early and more efficient mitigation efforts by managers and help prevent unnecessary public exposure to aerosolized toxins.

In fall 2010, NOAA similarly transitioned a “demonstration,” or proof of concept, HAB forecast for the western Gulf of Mexico (Texas) to operational capability. Texas forecasts focus primarily on early warnings for *K. brevis*, but detecting toxic *Dinophysis acuminata* and modeling potential transport of blooms along the coast is also supported. Texas forecasts also incorporate data from a continuous automated imaging sensor designed by researchers at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution and operated by Texas A&M University scientists, called Imaging FlowCytobot, that captures images of phytoplankton for validation and enhanced early warning capabilities.

Demonstrations have been underway in several regions within the US for some time: 1) for the past three years in Lake Erie, targeting toxic *Microcystis* blooms (by NOAA), 2) for the past five years in the Gulf of Maine targeting toxic *Alexandrium* blooms (by the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution and North Carolina State University), and 3) for the past four years in the Pacific Northwest targeting toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia* blooms (by the University of Washington and NOAA). Several hundred managers representing dozens of federal, state, and local agencies receive and use information from these experimental systems to better manage resources and to mitigate public health and economic impacts. Regional HAB forecasts for the Chesapeake Bay and the California coast are

also under development. Plans are already being developed to transition the Great Lakes, Gulf of Maine, and Pacific Northwest regional forecasts to operations in NOAA’s Center for Operational Oceanographic Products and Services (CO-OPS), in collaboration with state and academic partners, <http://www.tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/hab/development.html>.

The Importance of Research

The development of successful, integrated ecological forecasting systems begins with research that includes an understanding of the regional HAB species ecology and oceanography. For example, the harmful algal bloom forecast system for the Gulf of Maine uses a coupled biological/physical model based on such understanding along with *Alexandrium* cyst maps to generate a seasonal forecast of bloom severity—comparable to seasonal climate outlooks. During the bloom season, weekly forecasts of bloom development, transport, and decline are issued. This success has developed over fifteen years, starting with a major regional project to understand the ecology of *Alexandrium* blooms, funded first by NOAA and the National Science Foundation (NSF) through the Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (ECO HAB) Program. The engagement of multiple funding sources has advanced the research to the present day forecast model for *Alexandrium*.

Research has played a similar role in the development of forecast systems in other regions of the U.S. and will continue into the future, both to improve existing forecasts and develop new ones.

Future of HAB Forecasting in the U.S.

NOAA is taking an integrated approach to managing data synthesis, analysis, and dissemination to serve multiple operational forecasts for impacted regions, recognizing that HAB issues, the state of knowledge, and the components of HAB forecasts are different for each region.

For systems that are operational, both evaluations of the forecasts and

Sneezing? Coughing? Watery Eyes?

Your symptoms may be related to Florida Red Tide. People with asthma or respiratory problems should avoid red tide areas especially when winds are blowing on shore.

To speak to a health professional anytime, call the Florida Red Tide Health Hotline

1-888-232-8635 toll free

Breathe Easy During a Red Tide

new research discoveries continually identify necessary improvements and valuable enhancements. HAB-specific sensors, deployed on remotely operated vehicles, ships and moorings as part of coastal observing systems, will provide crucial data for more accurate predictions. Some next generation forecasts will incorporate food-web based models that predict fate and effects of HAB toxins. Long-term risk assessments to ecosystems will be important for resource management as well. These are a few examples of the exciting work that lies ahead.

Support for HAB modeling, detection, and forecasting is provided by many federal agencies, including NOAA, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), NSF, and the National Institute for Environmental Health and Safety (NIEHS). Continuing collaborations between Federal agencies (including funding programs, researchers, modelers, and operational offices), academia, state agencies, nonprofits, industry, etc. will be essential for continued success.

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Gambierdiscus Wiki

A *Gambierdiscus* Wiki has been developed on Wiki Spaces <http://gambierdiscuswiki.wikispaces.com/> as a GEOHAB-BHAB product. The taxonomy of *Gambierdiscus* will be evolving for quite some time and this is a forum for helping the community interact.

The aim is to get the information out so it can be used and other information added as the community contributes. Comments are welcome to Dr. Pat Tester at Pat.Tester@noaa.gov

Phycotoxins

You can also get news on HAB research and events at the Phycotoxins-list at the internet.

The address of this list is: phycotoxins@www.agr.ca

To join the list, send "subscribe phycotoxins" to: listserv@www.agr.ca

Archives are located at www.agr.ca/archives/phycotoxins.html

The “GEOHAB Core Research Project on HABs in Benthic Systems” presented at ICOD

The “International Conference of Ostreopsis Development” (ICOD) was held in Villefranche-sur-mer, last April 2011 (<http://www.obs-vlfr.fr/ICOD/>). During three days, scientists, policy makers and managers from the Mediterranean area and other countries exchanged their expertise in order to optimize the knowledge transfer and to reduce the risks linked to the *Ostreopsis* development. At the conference, communications covered many aspects of the ecology, chemistry and toxicology of *Ostreopsis* species. Fruitful discussions took place on how to approach the ecologic, economic and health management aspects of the problems caused by blooms of *Ostreopsis* species in the Mediterranean and around the world’s seas.

The ICOD deserved a special interest for the GEOHAB program, given its

tight link with the new Core Research Project (CRP) on “Harmful Algal Blooms in Benthic Systems” (BHABs) currently under development. At the ICOD, Adriana Zingone (GEOHAB-BHAB Committee) and Elisa Berdalet (vice-chair of GEOHAB) presented the GEOHAB program to the audience. Furthermore, they summarized the main outcomes of the open science meeting (OSM) held in June 2010 in Honolulu, which represented the start for the GEOHAB-BHABs CRP. At that meeting scientists working towards the understanding of how particular benthic phytoplankton species (e.g. *Gambierdiscus*, *Ostreopsis*, *Prorocentrum*) proliferate and cause harm, intensively exchanged their knowledge. During that OSM, research priorities and infrastructural gaps were identified regarding the taxonomy, distribu-

tion and ecology of benthic HABs. The outcomes of the open science meeting, including the state of the art in the field of BHABs and a research implementation plan, are part of a report currently in preparation. The ICOD was an excellent opportunity for establishing bridges of collaboration among scientists and managers involved on BHABs and to foster research in this field.

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From left to right: Adriana Zingone, Rodolphe Lemée (one of the ICOD organisers) and Elisa Berdalet.

Comparative methods for the study of harmful algae: the GEOHAB programme within an Iberian perspective

The Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) programme was present at the "XI Reunión Ibérica sobre Microalgas Tóxicas y Ficotoxinas" ("XI Iberian Meeting on Toxic Microalgae and Phycotoxins") held in Bilbao, from May 31st to June 2nd 2011 (<http://www.ehu.es/reunioniberica/>).

The GEOHAB reports were made available to participants and a specific presentation of the programme (Berdalet et al.) was offered to the audience. The general characteristics of GEOHAB were reviewed: interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research with an international scope using a comparative strategy, in order to advance the understanding of HAB dynamics. Implementation of GEOHAB goals is achieved through establishment of Core

Research Projects (CRPs) and Regional Programmes, that start with open science meetings, whose published Reports (also freely available at <http://www.geohab.info>) provide a synthesis of knowledge and needs, as well as a roadmap for the international community.

The presentation emphasized some processes related to HAB events occurring in waters surrounding the Iberian Peninsula (including the Canary Islands), that have contributed to the development and implementation of GEOHAB. The scenarios included, for instance, the Iberian upwelling system, thin layers in the Galician Rías, the Ebro Delta embayments and benthic HABs. The aspects considered in the different CRPs included biogeography, biodiversity and adaptive strategies of target

species, eutrophication, physical forcings, modeling and observation at different scales. Important open questions within each ongoing CRP were highlighted to attract further contributions from the scientists attending the XI Reunión Ibérica. Special emphasis was also made to encourage endorsement of ongoing HAB related projects to GEOHAB. The participants acknowledged the important role of GEOHAB for the advance of HAB research and expressed their desire for it to continue this role beyond 2013. In the picture, some participants at the meeting.

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From left to right: Monica Lion, Santiago Fraga, Elisa Berdalet, Teresa Moita, Beatriz Reguera, Emma Orive and Jorge Diogène

GEOHAB

Global Ecology and Oceanography of
Harmful Algal Blooms

GEOHAB Updates and News

The GEOHAB Science Steering Committee met recently to coordinate ongoing activities and make plans for the next few years. The SSC added Dr. Patricia Tester (NOAA, USA) to help represent the new Core Research Programme on Benthic HABs, and endorsed several new projects and activities including two workshops (see also the article about the “International Conference on *Ostreopsis* Development”).

Fig. 1. The GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee meeting in October 2011 at Dartington Hall, UK

Special Issue in the journal *Oceanology and Limnology*

Harmful algal blooms have been expanding globally, but it has been particularly pronounced in the coastal waters of Asia. One of the major reasons proposed for this expansion in both Asia and throughout the world is the increase of nutrient loading to our coastal waters. To address some of the scientific questions associated with this apparent trend, the GEOHAB Core Research Project on HABs and Eutrophication held its second open science meeting in Beijing, China (October 2009). Results from that meeting were recently published in a special issue of the Chinese journal *Oceanology and Limnology* (Volume 29, Number 4), comprised of 21 contributions ranging from nutrient utilization to physiology, modeling, and comparisons within and between systems.

GEOHAB Meetings—Save the Date!

There are several planned activities on the GEOHAB calendar—more information and updates are available at the GEOHAB website, www.GEOHAB.info.

29-31 May 2012
Victoria, Canada

GEOHAB Open Science Meeting: Progress in Interpreting Life History and Growth Dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms in Fjords and Coastal Embayments

22-24 August 2012
Monterey, CA USA

GEOHAB Stratified Systems Intercomparison Workshop: Reconciling Physical and Biological Measurements

25-27 April 2013
UNESCO, Paris

GEOHAB Open Science Meeting: The GEOHAB Legacy and the Future of International Cooperative Research

Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms

Endorsed Projects

As part of the GEOHAB Implementation Plan (2003), the GEOHAB programme solicits and endorses projects that implement a comparative approach to HAB research in Core Research, Targeted Research, Regional/National Research, and Framework Activities. During 2011, multiple projects have been submitted, and are highlighted below. Additional details can be found on the GEOHAB website (www.geohab.info), together with the endorsement request form.

Framework Activities

International Workshop on Fish-killing Marine Algae, 10-11 April 2011, Oslo, Norway. As part of the pilot project "Algefisk" -The effects of algae and algal toxins on fish health and food safety- financed by the Research Council of Norway, and with the co-sponsorship of the IOC UNESCO Harmful Algal Bloom Programme, held a small workshop on marine ichthyotoxic algae. The workshop brought together in an informal environment researchers working on ichthyotoxic algae, to share experiences, ideas and approaches to tackling this under-studied problem. The overall goal is to identify research that will bring better understanding of, and, in turn, improved mitigation options for managing, ichthyotoxic algal problems. Participants include algal biologists, fish pathologists, algal toxin chemists, and aquaculture industry representatives. The lead contact is Dr. Christopher Miles.

International Conference on *Ostreopsis* Development (ICOD), 4th to 8th April 2011 Villefranche-sur-mer (FRANCE). Several species belonging to the genus *Ostreopsis* (benthic dinoflagellates) are common in temperate seas and in particular in the Mediterra-

nean Sea. The ICOD aimed to review the knowledge on 1) ecological, chemical and toxicological aspects of *Ostreopsis* species and 2) on the different methods of ecologic, economic and health management of the problem. The ICOD facilitated the exchange between scientists, policy makers and managers of the Mediterranean and other temperate countries, in order to optimize the knowledge transfer and reduce the risks linked to the *Ostreopsis* development. The event was organised by the French Phycological Society, whose 2011 meeting was held the first two days of the event (4-5 April 2011).

Unveiling the biodiversity of marine benthic dinoflagellates at the beginning of the XXIst century. The project is writing and publishing a (reviewed) book about benthic dinoflagellates. This book will contribute to the benthic GEOHAB Core Research Project because it will summarize all the knowledge about benthic dinoflagellates, present the currently known species diversity and help identifying the taxa. The main part of the book will be taxonomy (species descriptions and illustrations) and thus present the first comprehensive identification help for benthic dinoflagellates. It will be a basic contribution to improve monitoring efforts in this area. The lead editor is Dr. Mona Hoppenrath.

Regional/National Research

Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms in the Philippines" (PhilHAB's). PHILHABs constitute the HAB research program in the Philippines and proposed to be implemented in three to six years (2009-2014). Results of which can be also useful inputs into the envisioned Asian GEOHAB. The main thrusts of the proposal are derived mainly from the scientific program of

SCOR-UNESCO's GEOHAB. The general objective of the PHILHABs program is to understand the critical factors and mechanisms underlying the population dynamics of HAB species in various oceanographic regimes particularly the Philippines. Results can be used as basis for monitoring and managing the occurrence, movement, toxicity and environmental effects of various types of HAB's (in the Philippines). The program also intends to develop methods and technologies relevant to the monitoring and management of HABs in the country. The lead contact is Dr. Rhodora Azanza.

Determination of adhesive strength, propagation mechanisms and methods of destruction of different life cycle stages of *Alexandrium catenella*. Is the northwards expansion of *Alexandrium catenella* from southern Chile determined by climate oceanographic features and/or by the increase of aquaculture activities? Blooms of *A. catenella* in Chile are events that have naturally occurred in the southernmost area of the country since 1972. However, these blooms have subsequently been observed in lower latitudes, specifically in areas where there has been a great development of salmon and mussel farming during the last two decades. The reasons for this observed trend are not well known. The present project has as first objective, to study and update the database in the study of the coastal areas of Chile affected by the *A. catenella* blooms in order to investigate the factors suspected as well as the influence of ENSO to affect the spreading of this species towards lower latitudes of Chile. The lead contact is Dr. Gemita Pizarro.

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GAMBOS: Estudio de la distribución de dos dinoflagelados bentónicos marinos *Gambierdiscus* y *Ostreopsis*, con especial detalle en la producción de toxinas y su relación con la salud pública (Study of the benthic marine dinoflagellates *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis*, with a special emphasis on the toxin production and its relationship to public health). The aim of this project is to characterize two recent phenomena in Spanish waters related to *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis*, which cause an increasing concern in the public health and tourism sectors and the determination of the involved toxins. The main hypothesis that arises is that recent ecological unbalances in the coastal rocky habitats have caused the proliferation of these microalgae which were in the past in low concentrations and did not cause any damage. The lead contact is Dr. José Franco Soler.

Introduced Alien species in the Portuguese estuaries and coastal areas: patterns of distribution, vectors and invading potential (INSPECT). The introduction of non-indigenous or alien species that might become invasive has increased with globalization.

This project aims to study the occurrence of marine alien species in Portuguese estuaries and coastal areas, evaluate the existence of environmental conditions that favor or prevent the establishment of potential invaders and increase public awareness on this threat.

The results are expected to clarify some aspects of the introduction processes, such as the relative importance of vectors of introduction of alien species, the identification of environmental conditions that favor or inhibit invaders, and species with enhanced invasive characteristics. Proposals on the definition of priority areas and species will be one of the outputs of this project, with the aim of supporting managers and decision makers on the allocation of re-

sources to prevent and/or mitigate the impacts of invaders. This project is also expected to increase the cooperation between the scientific community, administration representatives of different sectors and civil society, by having all partners working together to produce information that will be used in raising public awareness for the threats of alien species' introductions. The lead contact is Dr. Ana Amorim.

Regional/National Research

ECOHAB – Modeling favorable habitat areas for *Alexandrium catenella* in Puget Sound and evaluating the effects of climate change. The dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* produces a suite of potent neurotoxins that accumulate in shellfish and cause severe illness or death if contaminated shellfish are consumed by humans. *Alexandrium catenella* form dormant cysts that overwinter on the seafloor and provide the inoculum for toxic blooms the following summer when conditions become favorable again for growth of the motile cell. A 2005 survey of *A. catenella* cyst distribution in Puget Sound, Washington State, identified “seedbeds” with high cyst abundances that correspond to areas where shellfish frequently attain high levels of toxin. However, even at these sites, interannual variability in the magnitude of toxic events is high. The objectives of this project are to (I) determine interannual variations in *A. catenella* cyst distribution in Puget Sound, (II) quantify rates of cyst germination and vegetative growth for a range of temperature, salinity, and light conditions, (III) determine the presence/absence of an endogenous clock that regulates cyst germination, (IV) model favorable habitat areas for cyst germination and vegetative growth, (V) evaluate climate change impacts on favorable habitat areas, and (VI) establish a time series with sufficient depth to provide seasonal forecasts of toxic

blooms. The lead contact is Dr. Stephanie Moore.

Study of the genetic diversity and characterization of cultures of dinoflagellates from the genus *Dinophysis* (DIGEDINO). The knowledge about the genetic diversity of dinoflagellates populations is still scarce and at least in the Galician rías it is unknown if there exist homogeneous populations along time and space, or a succession of subpopulations or ecotypes displaying different toxicities. In the present project we propose (1) to study the genetic diversity of *Dinophysis* in natural samples and cultures during a yearly period, (2) to define hypothetical ecotypes on the basis of the physiological and morphological characterization of clonal cultures in the laboratory, (3) to study the genetic diversity in plastids of *Dinophysis* to confirm if they originate from a single source of they differ geographically, along time or among the studied species and (4) to design specific molecular probes for species/ecotypes of *Dinophysis*, testing their efficiency and reliability to detect these organisms in natural samples. The lead contact is Dr. Francisco Rodriguez.

Trends in Phytoplankton Diversity and Environmental Changes in Coastal Ecosystems (EDIPHYCE). Over the past decades, marine coastal ecosystems have been exposed to important and rapid environmental changes, mainly caused by human activities. In pelagic coastal systems, modifications of the structure of phytoplankton assemblages in relation with such perturbations have already been identified, thus affecting the whole trophic coastal marine food webs. Long-term phytoplanktonic data sets represent an inestimable source of information to better understand the past and to extrapolate and forecast the future. The objective of this project is to evaluate if and how phytoplankton diversity (including

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toxic species) has changed in relation with the main pressures that occurred along the French Atlantic coasts and the English Channel, i.e. eutrophication and climatic change. Using a multidisciplinary approach, we propose to carry out retrospective and prospective analyses of decadal resources regarding phytoplanktonic communities, available either in the frame of monitoring activities and hidden in living archives (the sediments) or manageable by computer models. The lead contact is Dr. Annie Chapelle.

Targeted Research

A Regional Cooperative Assessment of the genetic variability of HAB species in relation to their toxicity, population dynamics, and biogeography (ReCoHAB) – a comparative research initiative under GEOHAB Asia. The Project will, as a regional cooperative and comparative research project, focus on two types of HABs (toxin producers and high biomass producers) which are particularly poorly understood in terms of distribution, toxicity and management options. Research priorities for these two issues were defined in detail at two expert meetings. The goal is to improve prediction of HABs by determining the ecological and oceanographic mechanisms underlying their population dynamics, integrating biological, chemical, and physical studies supported by enhanced observational and modeling systems. This will be achieved through international regional cooperative research on HABs in ecosystem types sharing common features, comparing the key species involved, and the oceanographic processes that influence their population dynamics.

ECO HAB: A Regional Comparison of Upwelling and Coastal Land Use Patterns on the Development of HAB Hotspots Along the California Coast. California represents approximately 1,000 miles of the Pacific coastline of the U.S. and major fractions of the coastal economy and environmental resources of our nation. Alarming, blooms of harmful and toxic algae have increased in frequency and severity along this coast during the past few decades. Although several HAB organisms are present, *Pseudo-nitzschia* (Domoic Acid Poisoning) is rapidly becoming the single greatest threat and problem for human and ecosystem health, potentially eclipsing PSP in severity due to the diverse impacts on the economy through commercial fisheries and tourism, as well as via direct impacts on marine birds and mammals. Our primary objective is to develop a better understanding of the ecophysiological conditions leading to bloom and toxin initiation for *Pseudo-nitzschia*, by simultaneously comparing two “hot spots”, Monterey Bay and San Pedro, California. The lead contact is Dr. Raphael Kudela.

ASIMUTH (Applied Simulations and Integrated Modelling for the Understanding of Toxic and Harmful Algal Blooms). A collaborative project entitled “Applied Simulations and Integrated Modelling for the Understanding of Toxic and Harmful Algal Blooms” (ASIMUTH) held its initial partner meeting in Cork Ireland on the 14 and 15 December 2010. This FP7 funded project has 11 research and SME partners from Ireland, France, Spain, UK and Portugal. Through the ASIMUTH project, scientists and industry from these countries along Europe’s Atlantic Margin will form a network to produce the first realistic HAB advisory and forecasting capability to the European aquaculture industry. The project will be an applied downstream service of the MyOcean core project of Global Monitoring for

Environment and Security (GMES) which is a joint initiative of the European Commission and European Space Agency, which aims at achieving an autonomous and operational Earth observation (EO) capacity. The lead contact is Dr. Julie Maguire.

The effect of algae on fish health and food safety (AlgaFish). The main objective of this pilot project is to establish international partnerships and lay the foundation for an application for the project entitled “The effect of algae and algal toxins for fish health and food safety (AlgaFish)”. Marine algae are believed to be the cause of health problems in fish around the world. There is no longer fish farming in large parts of Southern Norway precisely because of toxic algae. The significance of algae and algal toxins for the industry in the rest of the country is very little understood. We will build an interdisciplinary network of Norwegian and international scientists to study the algae problems in connection with fish health, and then secure the knowledge needed to develop potential solutions. A pilot project is testing whether algae can be the cause of the seasonal gill damage in two fish farms in south-west Norway, and whether algal toxins may be the mechanism behind this. In addition, SPATT-disks will be tested to see whether they can be used for monitoring of algal toxins, including ichthyotoxins. The lead contact is Dr. Christopher Miles.

ISSHA

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

ISSHA's Corner

Dear ISSHA members:

The ISSHA Council wishes you a very productive 2012!

This year is a busy one and we will need your active participation for an important list of activities:

- Election of new Council Members
- Nominations for the Yasumoto life-time achievements award

- Nominations for the Patrick Gentien (Young scientist) award
- Bids to host the 17 ICHA Conference (2016)

Our Korean colleagues, coordinated by Dr Hak Gyoon KIM (full time dedication) are doing their best to prepare an impressive 15 ICHA Conference in Changwon (South Korea). Start thinking about the work you want to bring to Ko-

rea, ear mark the costs in your budgets, and consult the 15 ICHA website (available through the ISSHA website, www.issha.org). Do not leave everything for the last minute!

Many of you will soon receive a reminder to renew your membership dues.

Do not forget to add a portrait of yourself (login/my profile). It is so nice to be able to recognize faces.

Fig. 1. Participants in the Korean Local Organizing Committee (KLOC), convened by Dr H.G. Kim (KLOC Coordinator) held in Busan, South Korea, 1-2 December 2011.

Future events

Marine and Freshwater Toxins, Third Joint Symposium and AOAC Task Force Meeting and LC-MS/MS lab training on lipophilic toxins

18-22 & 25-26 June 2012, Tacoma, WA, USA.

Topics for the Symposium are the lipophilic toxins, the DSP outbreak in USA and Canada, saxitoxins official methods, domoic acid, emerging toxins, ciguatoxins, cyanotoxins and test kits.

Please reserve the following dates for above meeting June 18-22, then June 25-26, 2012 for LC-MS/MS lab training for diarrheic and other lipophilic toxins.

As many of you know, the US and Canada experienced their first outbreaks of diarrheic shellfish poisoning (DSP) this year right here in the Pacific Northwest. We will have training for detecting these toxins and a full day devoted to them at the above meeting.

Please contact James Hungerford (James.Hungerford@fda.hhs.gov) if you have interest in these sessions.

ICES/IOC/IMO Working Group on Ballast and Other Ship Vectors

12-14 March 2012, Lisbon, Portugal

WGBOSV is open to representatives from ICES and IOC Member States (the non-ICES countries). Indication of interest and further information: Tracy McCollin, tracy.mccollin@scotland.gsi.gov.uk.

ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics

25-28 April 2012, Oban, United Kingdom

WGHABD is open to representatives from ICES and IOC Member States (the non-ICES countries). Indication of interest and further information: Bengt Karlson, Bengt.Karlson@smhi.se.

GEOHAB Open Science Meeting: Progress in interpreting Life History and Growth Dynamics of Harmful Algal Blooms in Fjords and Coastal Environments

29-31 May 2012, Victoria, Canada

The GEOHAB Core Research Project (CRP) on HABs in Fjords and Coastal Embayments will hold an Open Science Meeting to review and update research on the role of life history and growth dynamics in the control of harmful algal blooms (HABs) in coastal environments and to identify key objectives for future international studies. Organizers: Allan Cembella, Leonardo Guzmán, Marina Montresor, Vera Pospelova and Suzanne Roy. Contact: Dr. S. Roy, Suzanne_Roy@uqar.ca

IOC Qualifications in Identification and Enumeration of Harmful Microalgae

15-25 August 2012, Copenhagen, Denmark

The course includes 90 hours of teaching and is divided into two parts, each consisting of 45 hours of teaching. The first part of the course is an internet teaching programme, while the second part is a practical workshop in species identification. More information: Jacob Larsen, jacobl@bio.ku.dk.

Future HAB Research Priorities Work Shop

28 October 2012, Changwon Gyeongnam, Korea

A GEOHAB meeting-workshop to present ideas and discuss HAB research priorities in the coming decades. For more information: Chair GEOHAB SSC, R. Kudela, kudela@ucsc.edu

15th ICHA 2012 Korea

15차 국제 적조 회의
XV International Conference on Harmful Algae

15th International Conference on Harmful Algae

29 Oct - 2 Nov 2012, Changwon Gyeongnam, Korea

HAB2012 aims to address all issues related to the causes and effects of marine and freshwater harmful micro- and macro-algae and to serve as a forum for exchanging research outcomes and relevant ideas between researchers, industries, governments and interested parties. More information: www.hab2012.kr

10th Advanced Phytoplankton Course: Taxonomy and Systematics

12 November - 1 December 2012, Copenhagen K, Denmark

The 10th Advanced Phytoplankton Course is being organized in cooperation by the Marine Biological Section of the Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen, Denmark, the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy, and the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae. The course will consist of training on specific recognition of marine planktonic algae, with emphasis on light microscopy and use of taxonomic literature. The aim of the course is to increase and update the expertise of the students in the identification of diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores and other phytoflagellates. More detailed information: <http://www.bi.ku.dk/apc10.html> or e-mail: apc10@bio.ku.dk.

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